

CHARACTERIZATION OF WOOD-POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE SANDWICH SYSTEM

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SUMMARY: Dynamic mechanical properties of a new wood-thermoplastic composite sandwich system are investigated. The wood- thermoplastic composite sandwich system was made by bonding unidirectional continuous glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (UCGPP) composite to wood using a thermoplastic tie layer. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) of neat wood and wood-UCGPP sandwich was carried out under controlled relative humidity (RH) and isothermal conditions to simulate moisture sorption/desorption processes. It is observed that under continuous desorption condition the modulus decrease is less in the case of wood-sandwich (20 %) when compared with neat wood (35 %). However, under desorption/sorption cycle (drying/wetting cycle) conditions the wood-sandwich seems to undergo significant modulus change when compared with neat wood. The modulus behavior of both wood and wood-sandwich with different end-use temperatures levels is studied. Optical and environmental scanning electron micrographs show the distribution and penetration pattern of tie layer into wood as well as UCGPP composite.

KEYWORDS: wood-sandwich, glass transition temperature, tie layer, plasticization, penetration, moisture content, hardwood, mechanical interlocking

INTRODUCTION

Synergistic combination of wood, synthetic fibers, thermoplastics and their composites, biomass and inorganic materials can meet the demanding requirements of construction, transportation, and submarine industries. Wood-thermoplastic composite sandwich is one of the attractive alternatives to the existing techniques for the utilization of wood. Thermoplastic composites have several advantages, including weight reduction, short cycle-time, moisture resistance, increased toughness, and potential for recycling. Strong fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites could partly substitute for larger and heavier all-wood construction, thereby using less wood and minimizing mechanical property variability and creep. Thermoplastic composites, especially made from commodity plastics such as polypropylene, become potential structural candidates for bonding with wood. The bonding between oak wood and unidirectional continuous glass fiber

reinforced polypropylene (UCGPP) composite was achieved by placing a thermoplastic tie layer during fusion bonding. The tie layers increasingly serve the purpose of bonding dissimilar materials such as polar and non-polar polymer substrates, wood and metals.

As the wood and wood-based composites are subjected to different load levels and vibrations in service conditions, DMA serves as a means to predict their long-term performance. Birkinshaw et al. [1] investigated the dynamic mechanical properties of ten types of timbers and determined the specific dynamic moduli and two types of transitions, one at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the another at $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Mechanical damping and stress relaxation on pine veneer samples under stepwise humidity changes were investigated by Ebrahimzadeh and Kubat [2]. Armstrong and Kingston [3] observed that the rate of creep of wood under sorption is much higher when compared to that at any constant moisture content. A thorough understanding of wood microstructure, surface morphology and the effect of wood moisture are also necessary as it would help understand the mechanism of adhesion better. In the present work, we study the dynamic mechanical properties of the wood-sandwich system produced from oak wood, UCGPP composite and a thermoplastic tie layer.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Oak was used as the wood member. Unidirectional continuous glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (UCGPP) composite was produced by consolidating commingled glass fiber polypropylene. Compression molding technique was used to develop the wood-UCGPP sandwich. Both oak wood and UCGPP composite panel were preheated to $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an oven and then placed in the compression-molding unit. Further heating up to $190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was achieved by heating only the corresponding bonding surfaces with hot air gun. The heating with hot air gun was carried out for a period of ~ 120 seconds until the surface reaches $190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After heating, both the bonding surfaces were pressed immediately to ~ 50 psi at a forming speed of approximately 100 mm/s with an air-operated press, resulting in fusion bonding. After pressure application, the bonded-assembly was allowed to cool under pressure so as to complete the bonding developed at the interface.

We used a DMA 2980 Thermal Analyzer, TA Instruments, Inc., to carry out the tests. DMA analysis was carried out on neat oak wood with following moisture levels: normal wood with about 10 % inherent moisture, and dry wood with 0 % moisture obtained after drying at $72\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 hours. The sandwich coupons for DMA testing were machined from the bulk laminates ($120\text{ mm} \times 50\text{ mm} \times 13.5\text{ mm}$) using milling machine to the dimensions of $60\text{ mm} \times 14.5\text{ mm} \times 5.5\text{ mm}$. All the DMA experiments with sandwich and neat wood were carried out with three point bending mode at a heating rate of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C/min}$ with wood section at the top and the PP composite at the bottom. The T_g and modulus of $0.11 \pm 0.05\text{ mm}$ thick tie layer was also determined by DMA under film tension mode at a heating rate of $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C/min}$. The DMA tests were designed to monitor the effects that the continuous desorption process and desorption/sorption (drying/wetting) cycles had on the modulus of neat wood and wood-sandwich. These isothermal experiments were conducted at $32\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a period of 180 min. Airflow rate was maintained at 1000 mL/min in all the experiments. The drying/wetting cycle experiments had the following

sequences: desorption with 2 % RH air / sorption with 85 % RH air/ desorption with 2 % RH air. The interphase of the wood-tie layer-UCGPP composite was examined both at transverse and longitudinal cross-sections by a Nikon optical microscope. ESEM micrographs of the wood-sandwich cross sections were taken with an Environmental SEM system (Philips Electroscan 2020, version 3.2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Dynamic mechanical analysis

The DMA results of undried oak wood show three types of transitions (T_g): α_1 transition at 231.0 °C, α_2 at 127.7 °C, and β at -46.9 °C, whereas the dry wood has α_1 transition at 233.1, α_2 at 147.5, and β at -34.7 °C. Due to the removal of inherent moisture, the glass transition temperatures of dry wood increased in all transitions. This increase clearly demonstrates the plasticizing efficiency of water. Kelly et al. [4] have reported the T_g of spruce and maple wood at 10 % moisture content, namely, α_1 at 80-100, α_2 at 10-60 and β at -90 to -110 deg C. Clearly, oak wood exhibits α_1 transition at a much higher temperature. The results of DMA testing of thermoplastic tie layer show the T_g to be at -54 °C. It can be inferred that at the end-use temperature range, from -30 to 60 °C, the tie layer would be tough and hence be able to exhibit better damping characteristics.

Effect of controlled relative humidity (RH) and temperature

It is understood that environmental conditions have a significant effect on the viscoelastic properties and hence the service performance of polymers. For outdoor polymer-based structures, the moisture content varies with the climatic conditions, the time of day, and the season of the year. Hence the study of wood-UCGPP sandwich under controlled RH and humidity conditions is of interest. Figure 1 shows the influence of continuous desorption condition on wood and wood-sandwich. Both wood and wood-sandwich display a dramatic rise in modulus during the early period of the absorption process (initial 10 minutes), as the moisture content within the material equilibrated followed by a gradual increase over a period of 180 min. Neat wood shows about 35 % increase in modulus whereas the wood-sandwich exhibits only 20% increase due to desorption caused by dry air. Under constant continuous desorption, wood-sandwich experiences less modulus change when compared with neat wood. Sandwiching of wood with UCGPP composite helps reduce the variation in modulus under continuous desorption condition.

Figure 1. Effect of moisture desorption on the modulus of wood and wood-sandwich system

The effect of desorption/sorption cycles on the modulus of wood and wood-sandwich is presented in Figure 2. In the initial desorption period both wood and wood-sandwich behaved in a similar manner. However, during sorption the wood-sandwich exhibits a significant rise in the modulus, whereas the neat wood shows a slight decrease in modulus due to plasticization effect of moisture. The modulus increase in the case of wood-sandwich is due to the fact that when the relative humidity is increased the wood swells and its elastic modulus decreases differentially to UCGPP, leading to the transfer of load from wood to UCGPP.

Figure 2: Modulus behavior of wood and sandwich under cyclic moisture conditions

As the wood swells and creeps, the UCGPP responds to the dynamic oscillation exhibiting its modulus. This change in modulus behavior between neat wood and wood-sandwich can be ascribed to differential shrinkage and differential swelling occurring during sorption and desorption cycles respectively. The second desorption cycle shows a tendency to revert to the original modulus levels. This increase in modulus means that even though wood creeps under high humidity, the presence of UCGPP would prevent further creeping of the sandwich. This behavior can also be explained at the molecular level. During sorption and desorption of wood, new hydrogen bonds are formed and broken respectively. Every temporary break of a hydrogen bond during drying cycle will give rise to a temporary weakening of the wood and a slightly increased strain in response to a fixed applied stress. During sorption of water, there is a partial recovery of the strain against the applied load.

We measured the storage modulus of both dry and moisture-conditioned wood-sandwich system at a wide end-use temperature range to assess the service performance. We observed that the dry as well as moisture conditioned wood-sandwiches, respond in a similar manner. Both lost about 17% stiffness when the temperature was increased from -30 to 32 °C. When the temperature changes from room temperature to 60 °C, a significant difference in the stiffness change is noted. The extent of decrease is only 1.25 % in the case of dry sandwich system, whereas the moisture-conditioned system showed nearly 25% drop in modulus.

Penetration pattern by Optical Microscopy/ ESEM

Optical micrographs of the wood-sandwich clearly show the microscopic details of typical wood-tie layer-UCGPP composite interface and the various patterns of tie layer dispersion into wood and UCGPP composite substrates (Figure 3). During bonding process which involves simultaneous application of temperature (190 °C) and pressure (50 Psi), the tie layer melts, penetrates into both PP composite and wood substrates creating a strong mechanical interlocking. The original thickness of the tie layer prior to bonding is about 110 ± 10 μm and the thickness after bonding is only about 50 ± 5 μm . This decrease in thickness shows that about 50 % of the tie layer has distributed either into the UCGPP composite or wood, thereby providing good mechanical interlocking. The penetration of tie layer into wood is easier because of the presence of pores/micropores. Various factors such as local melt viscosity difference between tie layer and PP, the presence of glass fibers, and wood microstructure, determine the direction and the extent of penetration.

Yvonne and Paul [5] have studied the pathways of softwood and hardwood using liquid gallium penetration into *Pinus sylvestris* L., *Abies pectinata* D.C., and *Fagus sylvatica* L. They concluded that in softwood the liquid metal penetrated first into the longitudinal tracheids and subsequently into the rays through the cross-field-pitting, whereas in hardwood only vessels were penetrated. Oak being a hardwood, it is obvious that the tie layer penetration has occurred in cell vessels as evidenced in ESEM micrograph Figure 4. In oak, vessels mostly control the flow of fluids to other structural components, and wherever they are blocked with tyloses or deposits, the wood becomes impermeable. That is why we did not seem to observe any significant impregnation of tie layer into wood in some regions. The greater the penetrations of the tie layer resin into the wood, higher the adhesive failure at the tie layer-UCGPP composite.

Figure 3: Optical micrograph of polished wood-sandwich showing typical transverse cross-section

Figure 4: ESEM micrograph of wood-sandwich transverse cross-section (above) and its local magnification (below)

CONCLUSIONS

The controlled DMA experiments under desorption with dry air show that over a period of 180 min the wood-sandwich undergoes less modulus change when compared with neat wood. The service performance as indicated by drying/wetting moisture cycles study reveals that there is a significant rise in the modulus of the wood-sandwich due to the differential shrinkage and swelling of wood in relation to UCGPP. When the temperature increased from subzero to ambient temperature, both dry and normal wood-sandwich experienced about 17 % drop in modulus. However, when the temperature changes from room temperature to about 60 °C, the extent of modulus decrease is only 1.25 % in the case of dry sandwich system; on the other hand the moisture conditioned sandwich system showed nearly 25 % drop. Optical micrographs clearly showed the tie layer distribution/penetration has occurred into wood cell vessels and UCGPP composite substrates.

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